

Supplementary File for An Adaptive Privacy Protection Mechanism for Blockchain-based Academic Publishing Systems

TABLE SI: Correspondence Between Formal Symbols and Prototype (minimal)

Formal	Prototype / policy tag	Role
$(s, m, r), \Omega_{R/P/A}, V, \mathcal{I}$	Phase, review model, GetOrCreatePhaseIdentity	Identity partition Eq. (1)-(2)
$(s, d, l), \Omega_i$	PublishingPhase, DataSecLevel	Data partition
$P(s, d, l)$	GetEncryptionPolicyWithLevel	Eq. (3)
$\mathcal{E}(M, P), \mathcal{N}$	EncryptDataWithLevel participants[]	Eq. (4) Threshold / E2EE recipients

TABLE SII: Sub-Protocols: Inputs, Outputs, and Formal Targets

Protocol	I/O	Invokes
Π_{reg}	$(u, attr) \rightarrow u$ (stable u)	Registration
Π_{id}	$(u, s, p, r, m) \rightarrow \mathcal{I}(u, p, s, m, r)$	Eqs. (1)-(2)
Π_{mon}	$(State, ev) \rightarrow \Delta(s, d, l, m)$	Workflow/chaincode event
Π_{dec}	$(State, \Delta) \rightarrow (P_{new}, \mathcal{I}_{new})$	$P(s', d', l')$, $\mathcal{I}(u, p, s', m, r)$
Π_{sw}	$(State, P_{new}, \mathcal{I}_{new}) \rightarrow State' / \perp$	Switch
Π_{com}	$(M, s, d, l, \mathcal{N}, u, r, m, p) \rightarrow (C, Meta, h)$	$\mathcal{E}(M, P(s, d, l))$
Π_{ic}	ledger tuple \rightarrow txid	Fabric write

TABLE SIII: Security Goals per Sub-Protocol (linked to formal layer)

Protocol	Goal
Π_{reg}	Binding of off-chain u to stable real identity f_R
Π_{id}	Correct V on $\Omega_{R/P/A}$; deterministic \mathcal{I} ; unlinkability of π across s
Π_{dec}	P_{new} respects σ and Ω_i ; anti-downgrade on l
Π_{sw}	Authenticated switch; fresh K' ; atomicity w.r.t. P and \mathcal{I}
Π_{com}	\mathcal{E} confidentiality (IND-CCA for E_{ECDH} ; threshold secrecy for E_{SSS}/E_{MPC})
Π_{ic}	Tamper-evident binding of $h = H(M)$ to C

TABLE SIV: Adaptive vs. Static Baselines on the Fixed Eight-Step Profile ($|M| \approx 90$ B, $n=3$)

Scenario (s, d, l)	Adaptive	B1 (alg.-static)	B2 (phase-static)
1 Submission/Manuscript/L2	SSS	ECDH	ECDH
2 Submission/Message/L2	PRE	ECDH	ECDH
3 Review/Manuscript/L2	SSS	ECDH	ECDH
4 Review/Suppl.data / L2	PRE	ECDH	ECDH
5 Review/Message/L2	PRE	ECDH	ECDH
6 Review/Final rec./ L3	MPC	ECDH	ECDH
7 Publication/Manuscript / L2	SSS	ECDH	ECDH
8 Publication/Message/L0	PUBLIC	ECDH	PUBLIC
Rubric total (access structure)	34.10	24.00	22.00
T_{wf} Enc+Dec total (ms)	0.234	2.418	1.972

Note: Rubric scores per primitive: ECDH 3.0, SSS 5.0, PRE 4.2, MPC 5.5, PUBLIC 1.0 (mechanism-capability index, not bit strength). T_{wf} : mean over 100 full workflow; details in Table SVI. Sensitivity: ± 10 –20% univariate rubric perturbations preserve adaptive>B1 and adaptive>B2.

TABLE SV: Cryptographic Complexity and Micro-Benchmark Latency

Primitive	Enc/Dec complexity	$ M =90\text{ B}$	$ M =64\text{ KB}$
E_{ECDH}	$O(n \cdot \text{poly}(\lambda) + M) / O(\text{poly}(\lambda) + M)$	0.31	0.39
E_{SSS}	$O(n\lambda + M) / O(t\lambda + M)$	0.016	0.11
E_{PRE}	$O(\text{poly}(\lambda) + M) / O(\text{poly}(\lambda) + M)$	0.056	—
E_{MPC}	$O(n\lambda + M) / O(t\lambda + M)$	0.015	—
E_{pub}	$O(M) / O(M)$	<0.001	—
$P(s, d, l)$	$O(1)$ lookup	<0.001 ms (1900 calls)	

Note: Unless noted otherwise, latency values are means over 100 runs and represent encryption–decryption round-trip time in milliseconds. Notation: λ – security parameter; $|M|$ – payload size; n – number of participants; t – threshold. The 64 KB column reports a manuscript-sized payload, measured only for ECDH and SSS. Threshold settings: for E_{SSS} , $t = \lfloor n/2 \rfloor + 1$; for E_{MPC} , $t = \max\{2, \lfloor 2n/3 \rfloor\}$.

TABLE SVI: Multi-Algorithm Integration Overhead (mean ms; 100 iter.)

(a) Workflow total T_{wf} ($ M =90\text{ B}$, $n=3$, eight steps)			
Scheme	Adaptive	B1 (all ECDH)	B2 (all L1)
T_{wf} (ms)	0.234	2.418	1.972
(b) Scale: 64 KB manuscript Enc+Dec vs. n			
Primitive	$n=3$	$n=5$	$n=7$
ECDH	0.410	0.509	0.672
SSS	0.105	0.125	0.133

Note: (a) Each row is the mean cumulative Enc+Dec over eight (s, d, l) steps (Adaptive uses SSS/PRE/MPC/PUBLIC where registered; B1 forces Level 1 ECDH; B2 forces Level 1 per phase). $\Delta T_{\text{int}} = T_{\text{wf}}^{\text{adap}} - T_{\text{wf}}^{\text{B1}} = -2.184$ ms: adaptive integration reduces off-chain crypto vs. uniform ECDH. (b) PRE/MPC omitted—weakly dependent on n at fixed $|M|$; see Table SV for complexity.

TABLE SVII: Fixed Eight-Step Workflow Profile (adaptive arm security levels).

Step	Phase	Data type	Security level
1	Submission	Manuscript	Level 2
2	Submission	Message	Level 2
3	Review	Manuscript	Level 2
4	Review	Supplementary data	Level 2
5	Review	Message	Level 2
6	Review	Final recommendation	Level 3
7	Publication	Manuscript	Level 2
8	Publication	Message	Level 0

TABLE SVIII: Rubric Weights per Policy Type (mechanism-capability score, not bit strength).

Policy type	Weight
ECDH_HKDF	3.0
SSS	5.0
PROXY_REENCRYPTION	4.2
MPC	5.5
PUBLIC	1.0

TABLE SIX: Aggregate Rubric Scores under the Same Eight-Step Profile

Item	Score	Note
Ours (adaptive, Level 2/3 mix)	34.10	See Table SX.
B1 (uniform ECDH)	24.00	8×3.0 eight steps.
B2 (phase-static Level 1)	22.00	$7 \times \text{ECDH} + 1 \times \text{PUBLIC}$.
Gain vs. B1	+10.10	$34.10 - 24.00$.
Gain vs. B2	+12.10	$34.10 - 22.00$.

TABLE SX: Adaptive Profile: Step-Wise Policy Choice and Rubric Contribution (sum = 34.10).

No	Phase	Data type	Level	Policy	Rubric
1	Submission	Manuscript	2	SSS	5.0
2	Submission	Message	2	PRE	4.2
3	Review	Manuscript	2	SSS	5.0
4	Review	Sup. data	2	PRE	4.2
5	Review	Message	2	PRE	4.2
6	Review	Final recom.	3	MPC	5.5
7	Publication	Manuscript	2	SSS	5.0
8	Publication	Message	0	PUBLIC	1.0
				Total	34.10

TABLE SXI: deanonymization Attack Results for a Double-Blind Reviewer Queue under Metadata Leakage Scenarios (Institution, Email Domain, and Combined)

Scenario	Queue Size	Valid Targets	Uniquely Identified (candidate=1)	Ambiguous (candidate>1)	Deanonymization Success Rate	Ambiguity Rate	Avg Candidate Set Size
Metadata_Institution	100	100	0	100	0.00%	100.00%	100
Metadata_Email_Domain	100	100	0	100	0.00%	100.00%	100
Metadata_Combined_Leak	100	100	0	100	0.00%	100.00%	100

Note: All 100 reviewers share the same institution, email domain, or both, resulting in 0% deanonymization success rate and 100% ambiguity rate. The average candidate set size equals the total queue size (100).

TABLE SXII: Simulated deanonymization Attacks: Cross-Mode Linkage (Double-Blind and Single-Blind) within the Reviewing Phase (Reviewer)

Scenario	Queue Size	Uniquely Identified	Ambiguous	Deanonymization Success Rate	Ambiguity Rate	Avg Candidate Set Size	Cross-Mode Linkage Rate
Cross_Phase_	30	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	0	0.00%
Phase_Pseudonym	60	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	0	0.00%
	100	0	0	0.00%	0.00%	0	0.00%

Note: All evaluation targets were successfully protected (no unique identification). A zero in “Avg Candidate Set Size” indicates no valid candidate linkage. The cross-mode linkage rate remains 0% regardless of queue size.

TABLE SXIII: Compared Schemes and Measurement Semantics.

Notation	Description	Metric
Ours (adaptive)	Data Policy selects ECDH / SSS / PRE / MPC / PUBLIC by phase \times data type \times security level.	Sum of rubric weights over the profile.
B1	Uniform E2EE ECDH: every step scored as ECDH_HKDF.	Common blockchain E2EE baseline.
B2	Phase-static Level 1: ECDH for submission and review; publication messages PUB-LIC; other publication steps ECDH.	Simplified baseline without level-driven upgrades.
Check A	ECDH: decryption by a non-participant.	Expect failure (PASS).
Check B	SSS: decrypt with fewer than t shares.	Expect failure (PASS).

TABLE SXIV: Unit Tests and Outcome

Test	Meaning	Result
TestSecurityScore_AdaptiveExceedsUniformECDH	Adaptive total > B1.	PASS
TestSecurityScore_AdaptiveExceedsPhaseStaticLevel1	Adaptive total > B2.	PASS
TestECDH_WrongParticipantCannotDecrypt	Non-participant cannot decrypt.	PASS
TestSSS_DecryptFailsBelowThreshold	Sub-threshold shares cannot recover the key.	PASS